

WEBSITE
SURVEY PISANG
PPTIK ITB

Tim Penyusun :

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Cara penggunaan website

Website ini merupakan website untuk memonitoring hasil report dari aplikasi surveypisang.

Link website : <http://survey-pisang.pptik.id/#/>

Tampilan awal anda di minta:

Email:

Password:

Silahkan login sebagai admin.

Tampilan setelah login:

Tampilan Cek data:

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `survey-pisang.pptik.id/#/`. At the top, there are two buttons: **Cek Data** and **Unduh Excel**. Below these are four summary cards:

- Total Pengguna Hadir Hari Ini: 2
- Total Pengguna Minggu Hari Ini: 2
- Total Pengguna Hadir Bulan Ini: 5
- Total Pengguna Hadir Tahun Ini: 6

Below the summary cards is a table with the following columns: **Nama**, **Tanggal**, **Komentar**, **Lokasi**, and **Gambar**.

Nama	Tanggal	Komentar	Lokasi	Gambar
Irma Handayani	14 Juli 2021 20:02:40	sedang mencoba aplikasi di unit 4	Unnamed Road, Catur Karya Buana Jaya, Banjar Margo, Kabupaten Tulangbawang, Lampung 34682, Indonesia	

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the time as 22:48 on 14/07/2021 and the weather as 21°C Kabut.

Tampilan Maps

The screenshot shows the map view of the Survey Pisang PPTIK application. The browser window title is "Survey Pisang PPTIK" and the URL is `survey-pisang.pptik.id/#/map`. The map displays a region in West Java, Indonesia, with a blue location pin over Bandung. A profile card for "Asep Trisna Setiawan" is visible on the left, featuring a photo of a man wearing a blue surgical mask and the text "diskusi".

On the right side, there is a "Tutup Panel" (Close Panel) dialog box with the following fields:

- Unit: Sunpride (dropdown menu)
- Tanggal: Rabu, 14 Juli 2021 (calendar icon)
- Cek Data** button

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the time as 22:50 on 14/07/2021 and the weather as 21°C Kabut.

